

Illegal and Harmful Content on Online Platforms: An Institutional Approach in the Case of Morocco

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ABSTRACT

This paper critically reviews the regulatory status of illegal and harmful content on online platforms in Morocco, considering local legal framework and international practices. It examines US and E.U approaches to control illegal and harmful content on online platforms and suggest an institutional approach for the case of Morocco. The finding of this study shows that evolvment illegal and harmful content on platforms could be controlled by coercive, normative, and mimetic mechanisms based on legal instruments, normative endeavor, and mimetic attempt to copy successful international best practices.

Keywords: Online Platform, Regulation, Morocco.

INTRODUCTION

The term content refers to “the principal substance (such as written matter, illustrations, or music) offered by a website”¹. Traditionally content was associated with written work, but nowadays it is widely linked to audio-visual creations hosted and disseminated by online platforms such as YouTube, Facebook, and Instagram.

Certain types of content might be illegal if they violate one or more legal provisions, either related to public order or individual rights, such as the protection of human dignity, privacy protection and child protection. Some forms of illegal content can be also criminal, such as terrorism, child pornography and human trafficking.

Other types of content, while not necessarily illegal, might still be harmful. This type of contents can offend individuals based on their religious believes, ethical standards, or other personal values and standards.

The prevalence of illegal and harmful content on online platforms is difficult to Estimate. Yet, based on reports from major social platforms designated as Gatekeepers by the European Digital Service Act, some relevant data can be derived.

In Europe, TikTok reports having 150 million monthly active users, with approximately 5 million pieces of content are removed by TikTok each month. Of this, 71% relates to child protection issues, 22% concerns regulated or restricted goods and activities and about 0,001% concerned harmful political, religion and cultural content.

Facebook, with around 260 million monthly users, reports removing about 4.5 M content each month. Among these removals, 16,4% concern adult nudity and sexual Activity, 6.6% relate to bullying and harassment, 3.4% to child abuse and exploitation, 8.4% to hate speech and 4% to violence and incitement to violence.

Instagram, with approximately 269.1 million monthly users, removed about 3,5 million content each month. Among these, 12,4% concern adult nudity and sexual Activity, 6.6% relate to bullying and harassment, 2.2% to child abuse and exploitation, 13.3% to hate speech and 9.5 % to violence and incitement to violence.

YouTube, with 416 million users, removes around 1 million content each month. Of these, 8,6% concern child safety, 70% are age-restricted content, 2.8% relate to harmful content, 8% to violence and 0,4% to harassment.

In the specific case of Morocco, these platforms do not publish detailed reports. However, according to government data requests, Meta2 declares receiving a total of 597 legal process requests from Moroccan authorities over a six-

¹ Merriam Webster dictionary <https://www.merriam-webster.com/>

² meta government report H1 2024 <https://transparency.meta.com/reports/government-data-requests/>

month period. Google's government report ³ indicates receiving just 4 suppression requests related to r defamation during the same period.

We believe that legal requests for content suppression by platforms do not fully reflect the prevalence of harmful and illegal content in Morocco, as not all reported cases lead to judicial complaints. This is particularly significant given that Morocco has 30 million social media users, 80% of whom are daily users, spending an average of 2,5 hours per day online.

Illegal and harmful online content represent a significant economic and social threat to nations worldwide, and Morocco is no exception... This study highlights the critical need for enhancing Morocco's legal and regulatory framework to address this threat. This research aims to answer the following questions: What model can be used to regulate platform in the specific context of Morocco?

The present document is structured in five sections: (2) platform regulation theories; (3) review and assessment of legal/regulatory framework in Morocco; (4) Discussion.

Regulatory and Legal Approaches

Since 1996, the European Commission has examined the problems and policy measures related to illegal and harmful online content.

The E.U highlighted the principle of "What is illegal offline remains illegal online", while also expressing at the same time concerns about inconsistent law enforcement due to the diversity of territorial legislation, ethical standards, and cultural norms.

At the time, E.U recommendations for addressing harmful and illegal online content focused on improving cooperation among member states co-operation; promoting self-regulation by internet service providers (ISPs) and encouraging technical measures such as filtering and rating platforms. While emphasizing doing so, the UE also stressed the importance of ensuring the free flow of information, in line with freedom of speech and public interests.

Liberal and neo-liberal theories

With the advent of Internet, many voices advocated for an Anarcho-Libertarian model of Internet governance (Bietty⁴), a model that promotes a self-managing cyberspace without any form state control. Later, liberal models also emphasized freedom but called for legal intervention.

The forementioned libertarian approach was initially applied to the Internet. However, Internet is no longer a 'free' distributed network, but a platform economy run by gatekeepers such as Alphabet and Amazon. These companies hold power through data control, algorithmic control, and economic control, which makes users dependent on them. The libertarian model, initially claimed by engineers and online platform lobbyist, reject state regulation and advocates for freedom of speech and innovation.

liberal models, while also advocating for free speech and self-regulation, propose some legal mechanisms, such as data privacy protections. The liberal model stance against the regulation of platforms emphasizes the importance of free speech and warns that excessive regulation could harm it. Regulating platforms could limit the power of incumbent giants like Facebook and Google, thus impeding free speech (Clyde⁵&al).

The second pillar of liberal model is the duty of care. Platforms can be seen as fiduciaries when they act in the user's best interest, with trust, free of harm, and without conflict of interest. According to Balkin⁶, this is an alternative, subtle regulation that considers privacy issues while respecting constitutional rights, in context of a fiduciary relationship. This model allows for the enactment of responsibilities for data controllers without breaching individual freedom. Hence, Balkin advocates for the fiduciary standard as a compromise, enabling customized privacy protections tailored to specific of data handlers, while aligning with Constitutional rights. This approach shifts the focus from regulating speech to regulating relationships of trust and responsibility.

³Google transparency report <https://transparencyreport.google.com/government-removals/overview>

⁴Bietti et al. ,A Genealogy of Digital Platform Regulation"

⁵ Clyde Wayne Crews Jr., The Case against Social Media Content Regulation: Reaffirming Congress' Duty to Protect Online Bias, 'Harmful Content,' and Dissident Speech from the Administrative State

⁶ Balkin, Information Fiduciaries, supra note 160, at 1221;Balkin, The Fiduciary Model

Liberal theory, emphasize on low application to online platforms especially Data protection laws.

Framework for data protection, especially the EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the different laws that exist in the US marked by its state-driven initiatives, have dominated platform policy.

In E.U, GDPR has become the standard for data protection in the world, forcing, among other, platforms to make users privacy on the first priorities. GDPR requests comprehensive data protections and transparency regarding how platforms gather and process data. Yet, in the USA, federal laws, such as the Federal Privacy Law, the Children's Online Privacy Protection Act (COPPA) or states law such as California Consumer Privacy Act (CCPA) tend to play similar role but their scope are far restricted to specific cases and population.

The GDPR delineates strict data handling principles, enforcing rigorous compliance. Platforms have had to implement 'privacy by design' and conduct Data Protection Impact Assessments. In the US, however, the lack of a unified federal regulation means platforms navigate a complex legal landscape, often adopting voluntary compliance standards that echo GDPR principles.

The GDPR's structured approach has led to significant improvements in data security practices, although challenges remain, such as cross-border data transfers and the enforcement consistency. Meanwhile, the US's fragmented legal framework has led to disparities in protection levels, with federal efforts like the proposed federal privacy law aiming to unify standards and enhance data security.

Neoliberalism and liberalism are both deregulatory ideologies that prioritize self-regulation, data protection, fiduciary duty, and competition. They emphasize freedom, individual choice, accountability, and competition. However, while liberalism views market freedom as a foundation for political freedom, neoliberals reverse this perspective, treating political freedom as a tool to promote and sustain free markets.

The Digital Services Act (DSA) is an EU regulation, enacted in 2022 to modernize and harmonizedigital service regulation as a continuation of the EU's e-Commerce Directive⁷ (2000). It applies to internet platforms, intermediaries and digital services based within the EU.

DSA focuses on User Protection to by reducing access to illegal content, goods, and services and giving users the ability to report illegal content. It also emphasizes on accountability and oversight by holding platforms responsible for illegal content and structural risk and implementing more robust controls. Other provisionsare stipulated by DSA like advertising transparency and fairness, openness of platform algorithms.

DSA classifiesplatform according to their size and function. Very large online platforms (VLOPs), defined as platforms with more than 45 million EU users, have more obligation. The main obligationsinclude:

Content Moderation and Reporting: Platforms must make it simple for users to report harmful content. When content is removed, users should be notified and given the opportunity to challenge the decision.

- Algorithmic Transparency: VLOPs must allow users the to refuse personalized content recommendations. Advertisers are required to disclose how algorithms rank or boost content.
- Advertising Rules: The DSA bans the personalization of advertising based on sensitive information (ethnicity, religion, sexual orientation) and prohibits ads targeting minors.
- Risk Assessments and Audits: VLOPs must assess threats related to disinformation, public health, and human rights. Compliance is monitored through independent audits every year.
- Crisis Response Mechanism: Provisions are in place for crisis like pandemics and wars where platforms help disseminate vital information.

To enforce theseprovisions, theDSA relies onoversight by the Digital Services Coordinators (DSCs) in each EU member state. VLOPs are primarily enforced by the European Commission, and unauthorized activities can incur penalties of up to 6% of the global revenue.

Institutional theory

Institutional theory stresses the interaction between cultural, normative, and structural aspects, providing a comprehensive view of organizations within their diverse environments (Scott). It moves beyond the strictly technical,

⁷Directive 2000/31/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 8 June 2000 on certain legal aspects of information society services, in particular electronic commerce, in the Internal Market ('Directive on electronic commerce') <https://eur-ex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2000/31/oj/eng?eliuri=eli%3Adir%3A2000%3A31%3Aoj&locale=en>

resource-focused conceptions and focuses instead on their symbolic and cultural dimensions. The theory argues that interests emerge and are institutionally shaped in ways that influence how goals and strategies are developed and executed.

Institutional theory identifies seven ways in which institutional factors determine organizational structures: i.) Imposition (Large groups of people, like governments or businesses, enforce structural changes); ii.) Authorization (Organizations voluntarily seek certification from third parties) iii.) Inducement (Motivation encourages organizations to adopt certain models) iv.) Acquisition (Organizations consciously adopt structural models that they consider appropriate or current) v.) Imprinting (Founding conditions leave lasting structural scars) vi.) Incorporation (Organizations modify forms by reflecting the richness of their environment) vii.) Bypassing (Social conventions and belief systems replace formal structures).

DiMaggio and Powell⁸ introduced the concept of institutional isomorphism, the process by which the institutions within a field adopt similar forms and practices. This mechanism includes: i.) Coercive Isomorphism (Arises from government, legal, or cultural pressures that force organizations to meet external demands for legitimacy; ii.) Mimetic Isomorphism (occurs in ambiguous situations where companies imitate seemingly successful competitors. This mimicry helps organizations cope with uncertainty but tends to prioritize legitimacy over efficiency) iii.) Normative Isomorphism (results from professionalization, where shared training, education and professional relationships create homogeneity among organizations. Professional standards and qualifications contribute to this normalization).

Institutional isomorphism explains why organizations within the same field tend to resemble each other, regardless of their origins and specific goals. It highlights the role of social and cultural influences on organizational behavior, with significant implications for the study of organizational diversity and change.

Legal framework in Morocco

The Moroccan legal framework against illegal and harmful online content combines national law, sector-specific regulations, and international obligations. Its objectives include protecting individuals from cyber risks, particularly children, and regulating content on digital mediums.

The Moroccan constitution⁹ of 2011 guarantees individual privacy and the protection of personal information, while also highlighting the importance of Child protection. Furthermore, Morocco has ratified international treaties with impact on online platform regulation as the Budapest Convention on Cybercrime¹⁰ and United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child¹¹ (UNCRC).

The Moroccan penal code addresses privacy violation by criminalizing the publication or posting of information, pictures, or data obtained without consent¹². It also criminalizes child pornography, including its production, distribution, and possession¹³. Furthermore, the code prohibits the publication of materials that promote violence, discrimination, hatred¹⁴, or content that incites terrorism or extremism¹⁵.

The Telecommunication Code¹⁶ requires telecom companies and ISPs to block access to illegal or harmful online content and mandates their cooperation with the government in removing such content from digital platforms.

Data protection is governed by law on Data Protection¹⁷, which prevents the misuse or unauthorized publication of individuals' personal information. It also sets stricter rules for collecting sensitive data, particularly concerning children and other vulnerable groups.

⁸DiMaggio, THE IRON CAGE REVISITED: INSTITUTIONAL ISOMORPHISM AND COLLECTIVE RATIONALITY IN ORGANIZATIONAL FIELDS DOI : 10.2307/2095101

⁹ Morocco constitution art. 24 and 32 <https://adala.justice.gov.ma/fr/resources/752>

¹⁰Convention on cybercrimes, Budapest <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/cmsdata/179163/20090225ATT50418EN.pdf>

¹¹United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child UNCRC <https://www.ohchr.org/en/instruments-mechanisms/instruments/convention-rights-child>

¹²Morocco penal code art. 447-1 through 447-3

[https://adala.justice.gov.ma/api/uploads/2024/04/30/CODE%20PENAL_compressed%20\(1\)-1714485942207.pdf](https://adala.justice.gov.ma/api/uploads/2024/04/30/CODE%20PENAL_compressed%20(1)-1714485942207.pdf)

¹³Morocco penal code, article 503-1-1

¹⁴Morocco penal code, article 267-5

¹⁵Morocco penal code, article 208

¹⁶Morocco telecom Act 24_96

¹⁷Morocco law on data protection

<https://adala.justice.gov.ma/api/uploads/2024/04/30/Protection%20des%20personnes%20physiques-1714464099884.pdf>

The Draft Law on social media and Digital Content¹⁸ regulate digital content to prevent the sharing of harmful, illegal, or fraudulent material. It requires the deletion of content that violates public order, morality, or rights. Additionally, the draft law places responsibility on platforms to collaborate with the law enforcement and includes penalties for both content creators and platforms that fail to comply.

Data protection laws and regulations in Morocco are primarily governed by law No. 09-08¹⁹ and its associated decrees.

Key Provisions include:

- Processing of personal data: both automated or manual processing in the public and private sector must be based on the consent of the individual, unless exemptions apply (e.g., legal obligations).
- Rights of data owners: individuals have the right to access, correct, delete, or object to the processing of their personal data.
- Data Controller Obligations: Organization must inform the National Commission for the Control of Personal Data Protection (CNDP) about their data processing activities, ensure data protection and privacy, and avoid transferring data to countries with inadequate data protection laws unless certain conditions are met. The CNDP regulates compliance with Law No. 09-08. Companies dealing with personal data in Morocco should:
 - Request authorization from CNDP for certain types of data processing.,
 - Conduct Data protection Impact Assessments for high-risk data processing.
 - Safeguard data against unauthorized access, modification, or deletion.
 - Notify CNDP and impacted people in the event of a significant data breach.
- Non-compliance with Law No. 09-08 may result in:
 - Administrative sanctions, such as warnings, denial, or suspension of data processing licenses.
 - Penalties, including imprisonment for severe violations, such as data leaks, or data misuse.

DISCUSSION

In section two, we demonstrate that content regulation is mainly represented by US on one side, which clearly follows a neo-liberal model. The US focuses on individual rights and freedom of speech in accordance with the first amendment of its constitution²⁰. US politics tends to protect the major online platforms, and thereby safeguarding its economy. On the other hand, the E.U, with its latest regulations such as the Digital Markets Act (DMA) and the Digital Services Act (DSA), enforces compliance among VLOP and other online platforms. European regulation is driven by user protection but can be also viewed as an attempt to curb the market power of US platforms and foster the development of European startups.

In section three, we present the current legal framework regarding illegal and harmful content on online platform. We identify that regulation is weak, with the primary reliance on Penal Code, to criminalize illegal online content. However, enforcing these provisions raises the significant issue of legal territoriality, as platforms are hosted in foreign countries and Moroccan laws are unlikely to be enforced abroad. Consequently, Moroccan laws can only affect Moroccan citizens who create or disseminate illegal content on foreign platforms which limits the effectiveness of law enforcement.

However, we noted that Moroccan legal provisions allow for ISPs to be requested to block or filter illegal content upon judiciary order. While this approach can be practical in certain cases, such technical measures cannot be effectively implemented without mechanisms to analyze the vast amounts of content distributed on platforms and identify illegal material. This is unlikely to be feasible given the time and resources needed.

Therefore, a national regulation of online platforms, based on National regulation like Germany's NetzDG²¹ seems more realistic for Morocco. Similarly, a community-based policy such as DSA cannot be directly applied in the Morocco local context.

¹⁸Draft law 22.20 on social media

¹⁹Law 09.08 on data protection

<https://adala.justice.gov.ma/api/uploads/2024/04/30/Protection%20des%20personnes%20physiques-1714464099884.pdf>

²⁰Constitution of the United States <https://www.senate.gov/about/origins-foundations/senate-and-constitution/constitution.htm>

²¹Law to Improve Law Enforcement in Social Networks (Network Enforcement Act - NetzDG)

<https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/netzdg/BJNR335210017.html>

We suggest that a policy based on the Institutional theory, with its three pillars: coercive, normative, and mimetic could serve as a viable compromise solution:

- Coercive: Morocco already has local laws, such as Penal code, Telecom Act, and data protection law, which have been recently amended to cover information systems and online activities.
- Normative: Morocco has ratified the Budapest Convention, which enables international cooperation between states to fight illegal online content. However, this alone is insufficient to address the full scope of illegal content.
- Mimetic: Morocco should mimic the approach of more advanced countries in addressing illegal online content. This could involve following international regulatory best practices when applicable.

CONCLUSION

The tremendous effort of online platforms raises new challenges for both Moroccan citizens and government. To address these challenges Morocco needs to evolve its regulatory framework concerning legal and harmful content on online platforms. We propose an approach based on institutional theory structure (coercive, normative, and mimetic). Legal frameworks in Morocco already address most of the infringement related to illegal online content. Equally, Morocco has ratified some international conventions and treaties on illegal content and child protection. Likewise, regulations on data protection seem to mimic the E.U. one.

Nevertheless, the complexity of legal framework enforcement should be mitigated with more international cooperation. Likewise, mimicking E.U. regulation on platforms needs to be addressed in a proper way taking into consideration intrinsic differences between Morocco and more economically developed countries.